

PHARMECO is officially launched and set to trigger a green revolution in the manufacture of medicines

We are thrilled to announce the official launch of the ambitious PHARMECO project, as of 1st of November 2024, co-funded by the Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking (IHI JU) and coordinated by Ghent University (CESPE), together with Sanofi as industry project lead. This groundbreaking initiative aims to transform pharmaceutical industry by adoption of more sustainable manufacturing practices. It will achieve this through the implementation of greener technologies and processes, the integration of sustainability steering methods at each stage of production, and the standardization of sustainability evaluation approaches across the sector.

PHARMECO will address the production of small molecules, tides, biologics, and medical devices & technologies, with a key focus on:

- Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) platforms for early-stage pharmaceutical development
- Green processes for industrial-scale manufacturing and decontamination
- Advanced digital tools for sustainability assessment and decision-making

31 distinguished international partners are excited to join forces through this alliance:

PHARMECO is committed to setting a new benchmark for more sustainable manufacturing, creating a path towards a greener future that benefits both industry and society.

Stay tuned for updates as we work on adopting more sustainable practices in pharmaceutical manufacturing!

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